

What Is a Recognisable Contribution?

On the Characteristics of OER Authorship

Sylvia Kullmann, Shahla Rasulzade

DIPF | Leibniz-Institute for Research and Information in Education,
Germany

{[s.kullmann](mailto:s.kullmann@ DIPF.de), [s.rasulzade](mailto:s.rasulzade@ DIPF.de)}@dipf.de

Abstract

The OER statistics framework aims to make university teaching more visible in science evaluation with scientometric methods. Open Educational Resources (OER) are the object of measurement. As an equivalent to scientific publications, OER have to meet quality criteria in terms of content and pedagogy. A sufficient personal contribution of OER authors also plays an important role. To determine the eligibility of OER for scientometric purposes, this paper proposes a three-step process that considers the nature of the work, the quality and the determination of a sufficient level of personal contribution. In case of OER versions, the delta between the previous and the current version represents the performance achieved and needs to be examined. The division of changes into Content-Neutral Changes (CNC; format and formal) and Content-Based Changes (CBC, content-related) is proposed. The categorisation can assist in the process. CBC indicate a higher likelihood of a sufficient level of personal contribution. As the identification of all changes, their categorisation and subsequent quality review is very time consuming, research into technical means of supporting this process is desirable.

Keywords: OER statistics framework; scientometrics; Responsible Research Assessment; Open Educational Resources; OER quality; authorship; OER versioning

1 Introduction

In line with Humboldt's ideal, research and teaching can be seen as a unit (Riedel, 1977; Weimer et al., 2024). In the context of science evaluation, this ideal is not yet sufficiently taken into account. So far, primarily output like peer reviewed scientific publications is considered and valued. The existing system has been widely criticised. The Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) movement aims to address current shortcomings and proposes alternatives that should enable a fairer and more comprehensive performance assessment (CoARA, 2022). The overarching aim is to expand the relevant performance categories and broaden the set of applied methods in science evaluation. Commitment to university teaching is also considered here. Initiatives like ACUMEN or OS-CAM, where researchers are invited to describe their performance in different areas, including teaching, showcase this intention on a qualitative basis (European Commission, 2017, 2023). In the context of quantitative based scientometric assessments an approach to reward teaching efforts by the measurement of teaching performance based on Open Educational Resources (OER) is proposed with the *OER statistics framework* (Kullmann & Weimer, 2024). Here, OER are understood as freely accessible resources that have been created specifically for teaching/learning purposes, are of sufficient quality and a sufficient *level of creation* (Kullmann, 2025).

Quality is seen as a critical aspect in relation to OER and can be considered from different perspectives. The content-based and pedagogical-didactic assessment of OER as teaching/learning material naturally plays the biggest role in the quality discourse. However, the quality assessment of OER is also an important topic for less obvious areas. This includes Scientometrics which considers OER as an object of measurement with the aim of recognizing teaching activities within the recognition and reward system of science. There are various assessment approaches for OER quality (Goger, 2012; Camilleri et al., 2014; Zawacki-Richter & Mayrberger, 2017; Müskens et al., 2022). None of these cover the assessment of authorship in the sense of a sufficient individual contribution to OER. Before the background of the OER lifecycle which gives reusing authors the right to amend, adapt and remix existing OER and publish newly created versions under their own name, the examination if these amendments meet a sufficient own contribution is specifically crucial.

As a theoretical contribution, this paper focuses on the key characteristics of a justified individual authorship of OER and their versions. The aim is to develop a deep understanding of what characterizes this sufficient level of contribution and to explore how it can be determined. For this reason, the concepts of a work and authorship in a legal sense are discussed which is expressed by the *level of creation* as a basic requirement in general. Furthermore, the characteristics of authorship in the context of scientific publications are examined. On this basis, criteria which can help to determine a sufficient and recognisable contribution regarding teaching/learning resources are explored. In addition, it is analysed which types of OER versions can be distinguished and how this can support the determination of OER versions which could be rewarded in the recognition and reward system of science. This further elaborates the OER definition for scientometric purposes on which the *OER statistics framework* is based on. Accordingly, the research questions are as follows:

- What is a sufficient personal contribution to OER (versions) and how can it be determined?
- Which types of OER versions can be distinguished?

The *OER statistics framework* section (Section 2) introduces the theoretical foundation and research background of this paper. The chosen research procedure is described in the *Approach* section (Section 3). The section *Recognisable work and authorship as quality features* (Section 4) discusses the question of which criteria could help to determine a recognisable personal contribution by re-using OER authors. The *Characteristics of OER versions* section (Section 5) discusses the various characteristics of OER versions that can arise through the OER lifecycle and proposes a categorisation of these versions. The *Discussion* section (Section 6) summarises and reflects on the findings.

2 Research Background: OER Statistics Framework

The aim of the *OER statistics framework* is to integrate teaching performance into the widely used and recognised scientometric approach to science evaluation (Kullmann & Weimer, 2024). The framework represents a theoretical

concept based on the special measurement object of OER and scientometric approaches. OER are placed alongside other academic output such as scientific publications as achievements worthy of recognition. In this context, OER as scientometric measurement objects are defined as follows (Kullmann, 2025):

OER are publicly available, freely accessible materials that have been created specifically for teaching/learning purposes and are of sufficient quality and level of creation. OER are divided into the categories of Dedicated Learning Content for learning materials primarily intended for learners, and Learning Design Content for supporting materials for teachers. OER also include contributions to a supportive OER ecosystem that facilitates the creation, use and dissemination of OER. This includes, for example, infrastructure elements developed for open teaching/learning purposes, such as OER repositories, OER-supportive working environments, editorial work, consulting services, training and other support services for OER authors.

The OER definition for scientometric purposes differs in certain respects from other widely used definitions (UNESCO, 2012; Orr et al., 2015; Atkins et al. 2007). The understanding of OER is broadened by the inclusion of non-openly licensed but freely available (no cost) OER which honours the publication of teaching/learning material as a step towards openness in teaching. It includes a narrowing down to materials created specifically for teaching/learning purposes. This is because the focus on services provided in the context of university teaching would be lost if other openly available scientific artifacts like publications were also understood to be OER which is often the case with more general OER definitions. In addition, contributions to an ecosystem that promotes OER are considered to reward the efforts of institutions in this regard. Furthermore, the requirement for sufficient content and pedagogical-didactic quality and a sufficient contribution of OER authors is decisive for the recognition of an achievement in the context of science evaluation. This applies in particular under the assumption that OER can be equated with other academic output such as scientific publications.

Openly licensed OER could be adjusted or amended by others. In this context, the OER lifecycle as outlined in Figure 1 must be considered. It comprises reuse scenarios of revision and remix as specified by Wiley (2021). In a revision, an existing OER is modified by a reusing author. In a remix, existing OER are combined to form a new OER. Both, revisions and remixes, result in OER versions. If an OER is to be recognized as an independent achievement in the context of scientometric analyses, this own achievement of authors must also be recognizable to a sufficient extent. Thus, the underly-

ing OER definition refers to a sufficient quality and a sufficient *level of creation* as mandatory prerequisites.

Fig. 1 OER lifecycle (Glahn et al., 2010)

Build on this understanding of OER, the *OER statistics framework* comprises scientometric indicators at the individual and institutional level. As outlined in Table 1 (see pp. 101–102), in addition to classic productivity, cooperation, resonance, openness and altmetric indicators, the *OER statistics framework* also includes innovative indicators for transfer and support. The transfer indicators serve to measure the transfer of knowledge from research to teaching and vice versa. The support indicators consider OER-related support services within institutions (OER ecosystem).

The *OER statistics framework* is a theoretical concept. As such, during its development, current practical limitations in the field of OER (e.g., weak reuse, difficulties in identifying all amended and published versions of OER) were deliberately not considered so as not to restrict the development too much from the outset. The framework is a contribution to a more inclusive future science evaluation as part of the RRA movement that is currently still developing dynamically. In the following, theoretical issues on the specific details of OER authorship are further elaborated which is essential for a real-world application of the *OER statistics framework* in the future.

Table 1: OER statistics framework

Individual Level	Institutional Level
<i>productivity indicators</i>	
total OER count	total OER count
number of “Dedicated Learning Content”	number of “Dedicated Learning Content” - granularity level 1 (single, atomic learning objects) - granularity level 2 (units from atomic learning objects) - granularity level 3 (collections of units) - granularity level 4 (set of courses leading to a degree)
number of “Learning Design Content”	number of “Learning Design Content”
year of first publication (academic age)	–
number of active years of OER publication (NAY)	–
number of OER per year (arithmetic average)	–
–	OER publication dynamics
–	indexed growth rate (trend) of OER
–	subject profile
<i>resonance indicators</i>	
total attributions (TA)	–
number of attributed OER (NA-OER)	–
proportion of attributed OER (PA-OER)	–
number of attributions per OER (arithmetic average) (CA-OER)	–
proportion of self-attributed in total attributions (%)	–
–	mean normalized attribution score (MNAS)
–	highly attributed OER
–	unattributed OER

<i>cooperation indicators</i>	
number of contributing authors (NCA)	–
number of OER publications as first author	–
sole-authored OER (SA)	–
co-authored OER (CA)	–
–	sector cooperation
–	most important co-publishing institutions
–	most important co-publishing partner countries
<i>openness indicators</i>	
number of OER with a high degree of openness	
number of OER with a medium degree of openness	
number of OER with a low degree of openness	
number of free of charge material	
<i>altmetrics indicators</i>	
downloads of OER	–
views of OER	–
bookmarks of OER	–
social media conversations about OER	–
number of blogposts	–
number of mentions in syllabi	–
<i>transfer indicators</i>	
attribution in an OER to research material	
citation in a research material to OER	
OER material resulting from research projects	
<i>support indicators</i>	
–	OER policy
OER certification	OER certifications
–	OER infrastructures
–	OER funding
–	OER services
–	OER community support

3 Approach

The purpose of this paper is to elaborate the requirements for OER as a work and for recognisable personal contributions of OER authors and re-using OER authors who modify existing OER and publish them under their own name. The sufficient *level of creation*, which is mentioned in the OER definition on which the *OER statistics framework* is based, is taken as the starting point and analysed in detail. In this paper the focus is on the situation in Germany with a significant OER movement. In order to grasp the essence of a recognisable OER authorship, at first the situation for peer reviewed scientific publications is examined as the *OER statistics framework* sees these as equivalents to OER. Regarding scientific output and the requirements of a justified authorship in this context, standards and documentation systems for publication-related achievements in science were considered. These include the German Research Foundation's announcements on authorship (DFG, 2022), the Contributors Roles Taxonomy (CRediT, n. d.) and quality criteria on resource-centred, content-based scientific peer reviews. The identified characteristics for a recognisable scientific work, justified authorship and a sufficient personal contribution to a scientific artifact were then transferred to teaching/learning resources in university teaching. In addition, possible forms of revisions and remixes which results in OER versions were analysed theoretically. Finally, a categorisation of change types that lead to OER versions is proposed which could support the determination of those eligible for recognition in the context of scientometric analysis.

4 Recognisable Work and OER Authorship as Quality Features

Whenever an artifact is created, the question arises as to whether this artifact is a 'work' and whether the creator(s) can claim authorship based on an own intellectual contribution to it. In the legal discourse, copyright law governs the legal requirements for a work and a legitimate authorship. The problem of identifying a sufficient own contribution to OER or OER versions by authors is an overarching issue that exists independently of the legal situation in individual countries. The detailed discussion of the issue with the starting

point of the *level of creation* is necessary to further elaborate the OER definition for scientometric purposes underlying the *OER statistics framework*. It serves to clarify what the *level of creation* is in detail, if it is actually sufficient for determining a comprehensive own contribution or whether a different concept is required at this point. The concept of the *level of creation* in the EU and Germany as a country with a strong OER community will serve as an example on which the fundamental issues can be explored.

German copyright law defines works protected by the law in § 2 UrhG (Urheberrechtsgesetz, 2021). The concept of a work and the sufficient *level of creation* are closely linked (Dreier & Nolte, 2006; Bisges, 2014; Ortland, 2023; Fischer, 2021). Works can take different representations. In § 2 UrhG, works of language, music and film, visual arts and scientific or technical works are explicitly named as examples. In addition, the existence of a personal intellectual creation is stated as a prerequisite for a work worthy of protection by the law. Required is a sensually perceptible form of the work, which must have been created primarily by a human creative activity. The work must have a certain degree of individuality, go beyond the general and every day and make a creative achievement of the author recognisable. Depending on the type of work, this can take very different forms and, in the case of linguistic works, for example, can be expressed through the type of wording or the order of a narrative thread (Fischer, 2023; Ring et al., 2021). In German copyright law, the lowest threshold of the *level of creation* is expressed by the ‘Kleine Münze’ (Bisges, 2014; El-Auwad & Fischer, 2021), which does not place very high demands on the intellectual achievement to be protected. For example, a few words such as in an advertising slogan or a certain combination of sounds in a jingle can be sufficient. Case law also shows that even works with little personal creative leeway on the part of the author can fulfil the necessary *level of creation*, as is the case with a chain-saw instruction manual (rf. BGH I ZR 147/89). This is also reflected in a judgement of the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU), which states that a text component consisting of eleven words can express the author’s own intellectual creation (rf. ECLI:EU:C:2009:465; Hugenholtz & Quintais, 2021).

Against the background of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the question of creative achievements generated with and by AI, Hugenholtz and Quintais (2021) have analysed what constitutes a work within the meaning of EU copyright law and how a sufficient *level of creation* must be defined to be able to claim authorship of a work. Based on the EU copyright law and the relevant

jurisdiction they developed a four-step test to answer the question if an AI-assisted output fulfils the requirements of a work. Even though this test is designed for AI output, the principles can also be applied to non-AI output. Test step 1 involves checking whether the subject matter is output from the literary, scientific or artistic domain and is therefore basically eligible to be recognized as a work. Test step 2 refers to the question if the output is the result of human intellectual effort which demands the necessity that a human being is involved in the creation of a work product on a cognitive basis. Test step 3 deals with the central question if a creator had a creative choice in the creation process. The emphasis here is on the fundamental existence of a creative freedom in the context of the creation of work. So, important is the existence of a sufficient creative space that could be filled by a creator. Test step 4 focuses on the assessment if the creativity is actually expressed in the final work. The test of Hugenholtz and Quintais focuses on the inner character of the *level of creation* as the minimum requirement for recognising authorship of a work. Based on the above, it is obvious that a sufficient *level of creation* cannot always be easily determined, which makes it necessary to examine individual cases when in doubt (Wandtke & Ostendorff, 2023).

Even though a sufficient *level of creation* is legally the basic requirement for the recognition of authorship for human achievements, the explicit examination of scientific work according to the aforementioned criteria is not the primary focus of assessments in the course of peer reviews as a central quality instrument in science. Rather, the fulfilment of the legal criteria is not explicitly examined but implicitly assumed. This seems to be fundamentally justified, since, on the one hand, scientific works can usually be assigned to one of the categories of works permitted under copyright law. On the other hand, the contributions of individuals to these works are usually comprehensive and complex. However, the prerequisite remains that the work results are not the pure result of AI. It is reasonable as the mere fulfilment of the *level of creation* requirements for recognising authorship of a scientific publication appears to be too low. Therefore, additional criteria are necessary to determine scientific authorship. Due to the differences to the legal *level of creation*, only the *level of personal contribution* will be referred to in the following as a broader concept.

Regarding scientific artifacts like publications, concerning justified authorship, the focus lies on the scientifically relevant contribution as a look at the guidelines for safeguarding good scientific practice of the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) shows. Guideline 14 states that an author is

someone who has made “a genuine, comprehensible contribution to the content of a scientific text, data or software publication”. Such a contribution therefore exists if a scientist has contributed in a “scientifically relevant manner to the development and conception of the research project or to the preparation, collection, procurement, provision of the data, software, sources or the analysis/evaluation or interpretation of the data, sources and the conclusions drawn from them or to the writing of the manuscript” (DFG, 2022). The associated negative catalogue specifies the requirements by excluding contributions that are considered insufficient for authorship (DFG, n. d.). Excluded are, for example, mere technical assistance in data collection or support by providing equipment or similar, the mere provision of data sets or existing research software and the mere reading of the manuscript without any substantial contribution to the content. As shown, the emphasis of the DFG statement is on the scientifically relevant manner of contributions. From the list of activities mentioned and the reference to the genuineness of science, it can be concluded that work results that lead to the creation of new findings and added value for the knowledge of a scientific area can be classified as an individual contribution worthy of recognition.

In addition to the DFG view, the Contributors Roles Taxonomy (CRediT, n. d.) should be mentioned. CRediT differentiates scientific authorship into 14 activities that are assumed to be performed by one or more authors during the creation of a scientific work, such as conceptualisation, data curation or writing of the original draft. The roles are not intended to define authorship conclusively, but rather to describe the work involved in the production of scientific publications as precisely as possible. In summary, from the DFG statement and the CRediT activities it can be deduced that the creation of new, scientifically relevant and value-adding contributions to a scientific field justifies recognition of performances.

Research on peer reviews as one of the central and internationally practiced quality assurance instances in science confirms this. Due to the underlying assumption of the *OER statistics framework* that OER can basically be equated with scientific publications as an established performance class of science evaluation, peer review which focuses on a delimitable resource and on its content is of particular relevance. The Review Quality Instrument (RQI; van Rooyen et al., 1999) proposes the importance of the research question, originality of the paper, strengths and weaknesses of the method and a comprehensible presentation and interpretation of the results as the basis for high-quality peer reviews. In a systematic literature review, Sizo et al. (2019)

have identified content quality, impact quality, writing quality and ethical aspects with regard to the performed research itself as well as formal integrity like the check of the correct referencing and the consideration of conflicts of interest by the authors as central criteria for a high-quality peer review. Allen et al. (2019) identified criteria for high-quality peer reviews, some of which relate to the manuscript to be reviewed and others to the review process itself. In relation to the manuscript, the criteria content integrity, described in more detail by content quality, content accuracy and content completeness, as well as content ethics with the aspects of research ethics and publication ethics are cited. Overall, the mentioned criteria with regard to peer review essentially represent quality criteria in terms of content and also relate to ethical guidelines of science. The accuracy, completeness and comprehensibility of the research documentation, the fulfilment of methodological correctness and formal requirements like correct referencing are therefore the basis for a recognisable publication. The importance of the research question and the impact quality as well as the originality of a contribution are considered to be relevant. The independency of the research and the absence of conflicts of interest also play a role.

For scientific contributions, based on the DFG requirements, CRediT and scientific peer review criteria, the determination of the sufficient *level of personal contribution* comprises three steps:

1. Work type and level of creation: The representation of the work under consideration must be considered. Work results that enable an independent, scientifically relevant contribution are basically eligible for recognition. These include, for example, publications or scientific software. In addition, the work must be the result of human activities. If these characteristics are present, it can be assumed that the *level of creation* is present as a minimum requirement for a recognizable intellectual work.
2. Quality: The quality of the scientific work in the field under consideration has to be assessed. Quality can be measured in the dimensions integrity, accuracy, comprehensiveness and research ethics with regard to research methods. Good scientific practice (including the independence of the research) is also crucial. In addition, the importance of the research question and the genuineness and originality of the research for the scientific field under consideration are prerequisites for a recognisable scientific work. The assumed impact also plays a role for a recognisable work which is strongly connected to the importance of the research question.

3. Level of personal contribution: To justify authorship and thus the sufficient *level of personal contribution* of an individual person involved in the creation of a recognisable scientific output, the emphasis is on the scientific relevance of the personal contribution as a qualitative requirement (qualitative dimension). In addition, a substantial scope of a contribution is necessary (quantitative dimension). Figure 2 outlines the connection and prerequisites between the concepts work and *level of creation* in a legal sense and the *level of personal contribution*.

Fig. 2 Recognisable work and sufficient level of personal contribution

With only one author, qualitative and quantitative requirements are relatively easy to handle. In this case, the identification of individual, clearly delimitable contributions is not necessary as this author alone is responsible for all aspects of an artifact. A different situation arises with multiple authorships. In this case, theoretically, the performance of each individual contributor has to be determined. Accordingly, each individual contribution must fulfil the requirements in terms of quality and quantity to justify personal authorship. At the same time, the artifact consisting of these individual contributions as

an overall result must be sufficient in qualitative and quantitative terms. In practice, it is assumed that in case of multiple authorships, the contributors jointly determine in a fair process who has made contributions worthy of recognition and to what extent. The decision is then usually expressed in the ranking of the authors, whereby the first author is awarded the largest contribution, and all other authors are listed in descending order according to their importance for the work. As a documentation of the contributions schemes like CRediT are used. As a rule, there is no external examination of the correctness of these provisions, for example, as part of the peer review.

Educational resources such as OER differ from scientific artifacts which serve to document research processes and results and reflect new findings. A contribution to the advancement of knowledge in a scientific field is not required, but instead primarily a contribution to the communication and understanding of existing domain knowledge in a science is, which should enable students to take on an independent role in research in the future. Thus, the criteria for determining the *level of personal contribution* to OER differ from those for scientific output. Teaching/learning materials are used to impart and practise existing knowledge. They must be correct in terms of content and reflect the current state of research when used in higher education. They must serve to train young academics in a field at different levels and topics and in an appropriate didactic manner. Therefore, the procedure for determining the recognition of work and authorship of scientific artifacts such as publications must be transferred to teaching/learning resources such as OER. The three-step process can be customised as follows:

1. Work type and level of creation: The eligibility of the work type must be checked as an entry requirement. OER can take many different representations that can be categorized in Dedicated Learning Content, Learning Design Content and contributions to a OER ecosystem (Kullmann, 2025). Concrete formats in the first two categories could be, for example, slides, exercises, videos, animations, simulations and tools for teachers to help lesson preparation. Overall, the concrete formats of recognisable achievements in the field of teaching and learning are not defined to the same extent as they are in the field of scientific work yet. It has to be considered, that not all types are eligible for a recognition as works due to legal definitions. For example, this applies to ideas and pure concepts, such as the schedule for a lesson or entire seminar (Fischer, 2021). In addition, the content must be the result of human activity. Thus, a corre-

sponding examination of whether a specific OER could be seen as a recognisable work is required at this point on an individual basis.

2. Quality: As for scientific output, sufficient quality is a mandatory prerequisite for recognisable OER (qualitative dimension). The special characteristics of educational resources and associated quality criteria stresses the differences to other scientific output. Regarding the qualitative dimension, the focus can therefore no longer be on a scientifically relevant contribution but must be shifted to the pedagogical-didactic area. At this point, criteria catalogues for the design of teaching/learning materials for universities come into play. In addition to checking the correctness of the content itself, quality criteria for teaching/learning resources consider the didactic characteristics (e.g., Müller & Sperl, 2016; Müller & Oeste-Reiß, 2019). Special sets of criteria exist for OER. The Instrument for Quality Assurance of OER (IQOER; Müskens et al., 2022) can be highlighted as particularly comprehensive with 16 criteria catalogues on content, pedagogical-didactic and technical features. The selection of suitable criteria for the comprehensive evaluation of teaching/learning materials represents a challenge of its own that must be addressed as part of the concrete implementation of the *OER statistics framework*, particularly at the institutional level. However, in order to answer the question posed in this paper about a sufficient own contribution, the detailed discussion of specific criteria for the implementation of quality assurance measures for OER would go beyond the scope.
3. Level of personal contribution: The sufficient *level of personal contribution* of participating authors must be determined. The qualitative focus is on a genuine and significant technical and pedagogical-didactic contribution to the teaching of a scientific field (e.g., collection of suitable topics/themes and didactical preparation). In addition, a substantial scope of the contribution is a prerequisite for recognition (quantitative dimension).

As with scientific output, in case of one-authored OER the assessment is easier to perform. The collaborative creation of an OER (multi-authorship) is also fundamentally no different from the creation of scientific artifacts such as publications. In this case, the authors as a team can determine and document who has contributed sufficiently in which way, based on their shared perspective. With OER versions things get more complicated. During adaptations, amendments or remixes, various contributions are made by one or more individuals at different points of time, the qualitative and quantitative dimensions of which must be determined to recognise the individual

achievement. The object of investigation here is therefore the delta to the initial version, in the case of multiple authorship further divided between all contributors. In addition, it is essential to review the entire work, the new OER version, to ensure that the changes were meaningful and the OER version remains to be a good teaching/learning material. At this point, it is worth taking a closer look at OER versions.

5 Characteristics of OER Versions

OER versions are a result of the OER lifecycle and represent the character and the basic idea of OER to a particularly high degree. The possibilities of open licences are fully reflected here. The lifecycle of OER can be understood through the series of interconnected stages. Wiley (2021) describes the possible reuse scenarios of the OER lifecycle with the five Rs: Retain, Reuse, Revise, Remix and Redistribute. These stages represent the various ways in which openly licensed OER can be engaged with and evolved over time: *Retain* refers to the right to make, own, and control copies of the content. *Reuse* allows for the use of content in a variety of ways, such as in classes, study groups, or websites. *Revise* gives users the ability to modify or alter the OER to suit their specific needs, such as translating it into another language or updating it with new information. *Remix* involves combining the original or revised content with other open materials to create something new. *Redistribute* enables users to share the original content, their revisions, or their remixes as OER versions with others. Among the stages in the OER lifecycle, adaptation – encompassing both Revise and Remix – plays a crucial role in the continual improvement and contextualization of educational resources. Adaptation refers to the process by which existing OER are modified or combined to better align with specific educational objectives, contexts, or learner needs. This process is fundamental to the flexibility and sustainability of OER. Revision and Remix are the two primary pathways through which adaptation occurs: Revise focuses on direct modifications, for example, to the design or the content itself. This might include updating outdated information, correcting errors, tailoring the content to a particular audience or rearranging parts of the OER in a different order. Remix allows for the creative combination of different OER or other openly licensed materials to create entirely new educational resources. Additional changes can be made to the

OER to be combined. In this case, there is a remix with simultaneous revision of one or more of the OER involved.

In her work on OER versioning, Schröder (2023) has provided a comprehensive analysis of the use cases of OER within the context of version management. Schröder emphasizes the importance of tracking and managing different versions of OER to ensure that users can access the most appropriate and up-to-date resources. She refers to versions as distinct iterations of OER that result from any modification or combination of existing materials, and outlines strategies for effectively managing these versions to maintain resource quality and accessibility. However, while Schröder's work provides valuable insights into the management of OER versions, it does not delve deeply into the specific characteristics of the changes that lead to the creation of these new versions. This will be examined in more detail below.

Technically, all changes made to an OER result in a new OER version. However, at the same time, not all alterations lead to a new version in a legal sense by constituting a work with a sufficient level of creation. Likewise, not every change results in a new version that is suitable for scientometric purposes, as the changes made achieve a sufficient level of personal contribution. Categorising the changes can provide more clarity about the nature of the revisions to an OER version and help determine a sufficient level of personal contribution. As Figure 3 shows, basically, two categories of changes can be distinguished.

Fig. 3 Changes in OER versions

Content-Neutral Changes (CNC) refer to modifications that do not significantly alter the substance of the OER content but instead focus on improving aspects like grammar, spelling, and visual formatting, which enhance the clarity and usability of the resource. Depending on the type of possible changes, CNC is further divided into formal and format changes. Formal changes comprise grammatical issues, syntactical adjustments, and translations executed through tool-based, potentially AI-driven, processes. Format changes cover changes in the document's appearance, ranging from font adjustments to structural reorganization, design perspectives, or technical requirements. Notably, formal and format changes aim at resource enhancement without substantially altering the content itself.

Conversely, the Content-Based Changes (CBC) group explicitly aims toward direct modifications to the content and/or context of the existing material. This group encompasses three distinct types of editorial interventions: adding, deletion, and replacement. Adding involves introducing new information or content to the existing material. This could include updating the resource with recent data, expanding on concepts to provide greater depth, or integrating new examples to enhance understanding. Deletion changes refer to the removal of content, which may be necessary for various reasons, such as eliminating outdated or irrelevant information, simplifying complex explanations, or adapting the material to better suit a specific audience, educational goal or pedagogic-didactic designs. Replacement changes are deletions and additions sequentially applied to the same segment of an OER. Thus, replacement emerges as a derivative of these two feasible editorial actions.

In the context of CBC, it is likely that various CNC will also be carried out. Accordingly, CBC represent more complex changes that are more likely to fulfil the qualitative and quantitative criteria for a sufficient *level of personal contribution* and thus an OER version worth of recognition. However, the categorization alone does not replace a substantive examination of the OER versions under consideration.

6 Discussion

The OER statistics aim at the scientometric recognition of achievements in the field of university teaching and place OER at the centre of attention as an object of measurement. In this way, OER are theoretically equated with other

outputs already recognised within science evaluation which is the case with peer reviewed scientific publications. However, for such an equation to be possible, the OER selected for the recognition of achievement must meet certain requirements. Eligibility can be determined in a three-stage process: Firstly, the eligibility of the work type should be checked. In a second step, the quality of the OER under consideration as a teaching/learning material has to be assessed. Thirdly, the *level of personal contribution* of the OER authors as an additional quality criterion must be determined. This goes beyond the basic requirement of the legal concept of a work and a recognisable authorship (*level of creation*) and makes sure, that domain-specific quality requirements are realised in a work (qualitative requirement). In addition, it takes the scope of personal contributions under consideration (quantitative requirement). Against this background, the OER definition (Kullmann, 2025) on which OER statistics are based needs to be adapted. The term '*level of creation*' must be replaced by the term '*level of personal contribution*'. The relevant section should therefore read as follows:

OER are publicly available, freely accessible materials that have been created specifically for teaching/learning purposes, are of sufficient quality and have a sufficient level of personal contribution from the authors involved.

With OER versions, the assessment of a sufficient *level of personal contribution* is particularly challenging. First of all, every change to an existing OER technically leads to a new OER version. Due to the nature of the changes, however, not all of these new OER versions achieve a sufficient *level of creation* as a basic (legal) requirement. Authorship cannot be claimed in these cases. The OER versions that achieve a sufficient *level of creation* do not necessarily have to achieve a sufficient *level of personal contribution* by the respective OER authors that justifies the recognition in the context of scientometric measurements. Whether a sufficient *level of personal contribution* has been achieved must be examined in detail. The subject of the examination is the delta between the previous version and the OER version based on it. In addition, it must be examined whether the changes made have resulted in a high-quality OER version overall.

The identification and categorization of changes to OER can be helpful in answering the question of whether an OER version is a recognisable work with a sufficient *level of personal contribution*. A basic distinction can be made between CNC with formal and format changes and CBC. CBC refer to changes to the content of an OER, i.e., the actual learning content. The occurrence of several CNCs in the context of a CBC is likely. Analysing the delta

between the source version of an existing OER and an OER version using CBC and CNC is a primarily technical process that involves a great deal of effort. Moreover, categorization is only the first step on the way to evaluating an OER version regarding its eligibility for scientometric consideration. The identified changes must be subjected to a qualitative and quantitative assessment in further steps, at the end of which a sufficient *level of personal contribution* by the reusing authors is determined or denied. However, the categorization of changes is a useful mean to support the assessment process.

The quality assessment mentioned above basically transfers the content-based peer review process for publications to OER. The demand for a comprehensive evaluation based on documented criteria such as the IQOER even goes beyond peer review procedures in some ways, as openly available criteria would provide transparent quality assurance that is comprehensible to all parties involved. The selection of appropriate criteria for conducting quality assessments of OER is an important task that needs to be addressed when implementing the *OER statistics framework* in practice. While it is relatively easy to assess the quality of collected materials at the individual level, it is more difficult at the institutional level when the volume of OER is very large. The question of what quality assurance approaches are appropriate in practice and how they could be implemented at this level should be the subject of further research. In addition to peer review as a strongly content-based method, other approaches to quality assurance in higher education should be explored and adapted to the needs of OER where possible.

In contrast to other educational institutions such as schools, not all university teachers have sufficient training in didactics (Salmhofer, 2020; Trautwein & Merkt, 2013; Postareff et al., 2007). The content of courses and teaching/learning materials is generally not monitored. The development of teaching content and its preparation is largely the sole responsibility of the teaching staff. The structured examination of teaching/learning materials according to predefined criteria would, on the one hand, demand a cultural change that affects the content-related and pedagogical-didactic monitoring of teaching performance. On the other hand, the work results of teachers without comprehensible pedagogical-didactic training would be judged according to standards that they would presumably not always be able to meet due to insufficient training in this area. The creation of high-quality teaching/learning materials is possible regardless of pedagogical or didactic training. However, this aspect can present an additional hurdle to the creation and publication of OER. It is therefore necessary to examine in what form and on which basis

quality assurance procedures for OER are possible and feasible in practice. However, this does not alter the need to require a sufficient *level of personal contribution* for OER to be recognized in the context of science evaluation. This is a resource intensive task. Technical support, for example, through AI technologies, is therefore desirable and should be subject of further research in this field. Of particular interest here is the extent to which the assessment of the qualitative and quantitative dimensions can be supported automatically according to predefined criteria.

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